

Who says beauty and wisdom can't go along well?

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For a long time, many people have thought that one cannot have both beauty and wisdom. Therefore, many jokes have spread around about the misplacement of beauty and wisdom.

Nonetheless, there's been no logic or evidence behind the belief and jokes.

One example follows. In human history, especially in the Western world, the Owl has long been considered the symbol of wisdom. The book "Wise Owl" by R. Berger could have a lot to tell about this belief [1].

In Eastern cultures, the same belief has been shared, too. For instance, the allegorical satire collection about Kingfisher [2] mentions the Owl as a symbol of the Wise or the Talented several times (in stories like "Miracle" or "GHG emissions").

So, the Owl can (or should) be Wise! How about Beautiful?

The World Nature Photography Awards 2024, given to photographer Chatree Lertsintanakorn, will answer this. (See below.)

Again, the Owl.

What constitutes this "mysterious Owl's eye" can be a whole lot more intriguing. But here, we solely focus on the photo's beauty. Clearly, the photo won the beauty contest largely due to the

Owl itself. Thus, we can concisely conclude the Owl is beautiful. Even more striking is the fact that the photo was taken in Thailand (Southeast Asian country), and the prize was judged by Western people.

Thus, it appears that the norm of beautifulness has been agreed upon by the two different worlds, at least as far as the Owl is concerned.

References

[1] Berger, R. (2009). *Wise Owl: The Ancient Symbol of Wisdom*. Sterling Publishing Company, Inc..

[2] Vuong, Q. H. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BoBG2NNHY6>

[3] Poore, E. (2024). Mesmerizing photo shows weird, scowling parasitic plant that looks like an owl. <https://www.livescience.com/animals/mesmerizing-photo-shows-weird-scowling-parasitic-plant-that-looks-like-a-owl>